

THE PRACTICAL SITUATION OF TEACHING THE LIFE AND CREATIVITY OF FREEDOM IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. In this article, the practical situation of teaching the life and work of Erkin Vahidov in higher education, the educational literature created today, the role and position of Erkin Vahidov in the Uzbek literature of the 20th century, and the life and work of the poet are presented. objectively elucidating important information based on evidence, the role of the ghazal genre in the poet's work, and several examples of methods for teaching the poet's work are discussed.

Key words. "Nido" saga, slides, video, multi-video, short documentaries, free writing method, text creation based on concepts.

Many textbooks have been created to study the work of our outstanding poet Erkin Vohidov, and these textbooks serve to introduce the younger generation to the poet's works. In particular, the creation of textbooks and textbooks that introduce the poet's work to students studying in higher education, instill a spirit of respect for national values in our students and youth, explain the need to study the poet's life and work by showing the life path of our great ancestors as an example, reveal the place of Uzbek writers and poets in the pursuit of the national idea using the example of Erkin Vohidov's work alone, and substantiate the poet's place and value in the treasury of our national spirituality and rich cultural heritage, once again proves the need to study the poet's work at every stage of education.

The purpose of this educational literature is to reveal the place and status of Erkin Vohidov in 20th-century Uzbek literature, to objectively illuminate important information about the poet's life and work based on evidence, to comprehensively reveal the place of the ghazal genre in the poet's work, to shed light on the creator's epic work, to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism, to promote the use of the poet's work and works in the path of enlightenment and development, to explain the spiritual and moral essence of the qualities such as philosophical observation, courage, selflessness, enlightenment, freedom, and honesty that were the basis of Erkin Vohidov's life path and work, and their importance in the development of today's youth, to explain the creative products created by Erkin Vohidov as a poet: the epics "Nido", "Ruhlar isyoni", the

comedy "Oltin devor", "Yoshlik The tasks are set to analyze the essence, meaning, and ideological goals of the collections "Living Planets", "Eastern Coast", translations, scientific articles from the perspective of today.

To achieve these tasks, it is said that lessons will be organized using slides, video, multivideo, short documentaries, as well as traditional and advanced teaching methods, including express surveys, test surveys, programmatic teaching, roundtable discussions, and problem-based teaching techniques.

There is not enough time allocated in higher education to study the poet's work, and students will need to make effective use of the assigned lessons. Therefore, we will consider several methods and techniques.

"LET'S LEARN TOGETHER" TECHNIQUE

Together learning: the group is divided into small groups. Each small group becomes an expert in some area of the topic being studied and teaches others.

Structure of the process of organizing work in groups using the "Let's Learn Together" technology

1. Small groups of 5-6 students are formed, they are given names based on the students' suggestions.
2. Each small group is given one task - a part of the general topic, on which the entire study group will work, and they are provided with expert sheets.
3. A general task is distributed within each group.
4. Everyone completes an individual task.
5. Mini-lectures of all group members are listened to. They form a general result and prepare it for presentation.
6. The leader presents the results of the group work.

Rules for working in groups

Listen carefully to your partner.

Actively participate in group work, approach the assigned tasks responsibly.

If you need help, be sure to ask.

If you need help, be sure to help.

Everyone must participate in evaluating the results of group activities.

We need to know for sure:

A. We learn ourselves by teaching others.

B. We are in the same boat: we either sail together or sink together.

Criteria for evaluating the work results of expert groups

Criteria	Maks. Ball	1	2	3	4	5
Completeness of information	1,0					
Representation of information in graphic form	0,6					
Group activity	0,4					
Total points	2					
Total points	2					

1. Free writing method. Students are divided into small groups. Students are invited to write down all the thoughts that come to their mind on Erkin Vohidov’s epic poem “Nido” without stopping within five minutes. When the five minutes are up, “five minutes are up” is announced and another minute is given to complete the work. Because the main, primary, clear thoughts are usually born in the last, most critical situations. They are invited to read what they have written to their partners.

The teacher announces that the allotted time has ended and asks everyone to stop working. At this stage, the teacher has many options. For example, he can invite pairs to share their thoughts with the whole group and create a “Brainstorming” situation based on the ideas of the groups.

2. Creating a text based on concepts. The method of “composing a text based on concepts” is included in the category of independent work of the cognitive-research type, which requires various logical operations: analysis and generalization, comparison of evidence and phenomena, identification of common and different aspects in them, separation of main and secondary signs, revealing cause-and-effect relationships, etc. Usually, students encounter unknown phenomena, new materials, a problematic situation arises that requires the acquisition of new knowledge and the search for ways to solve the educational problem.

Rules for using this method:

First, the teacher announces a new topic. After giving a brief description of the topic, he separates the concepts related to the topic and presents them to the

students. Then, students independently compose a text based on the concepts given, using the textbook or relying on their previous knowledge.

For example, on the topic “Erkin Vohidov’s life and creative path”:

1. War, dedication, father, Tal'at, twenty years, Rustam, train, Khol aka.
2. Oltiarik, teacher, Gayratiy, Tashkent, university, “Morning breath”.
3. Narration, Nazrul Islam, Calcutta, freedom, judge, eternity, Aurangzeb, Hindu and Muslim, Shahjahan.
4. Byron, Pamir, Navoi, Pushkin, Afrosiyob, Mirzo Babur.
5. Humility, poet, ghazal, epic, native language, Uzbekistan, love.

Students compose a text in a short period of time. The teacher teaches several of them. Taking into account the time, the remaining students are asked to provide texts that contain ideas that are not repeated in the texts read above. In this way, the best connected texts are highlighted and the students are encouraged. This will help students delve deeper into the subject.

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